

A study of the relationship between employee empowerment and job satisfaction

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Abstract- This paper presents the relationship and impact of employee empowerment on job satisfaction. The objective of this study is to measure the relationship between employee empowerment and job satisfaction. Employees are the most important resource for any organization, so it is the duty of the organization to focus on the feelings, needs, health of all the employees. Employees are more likely to strive for better performance when they are given decision-making authority and responsibility. Both primary and secondary data were used for the study. Data were collected from 100 employees of manufacturing industries in Tricity (Chandigarh, Panchkula and Mohali) using questionnaire method in primary sources. Secondary sources such as relevant text books, historical events, journal articles, reviews, research papers, scholarly literature, and web-based resources were used. Descriptive method was used for this study. SPSS was used for analysis. Data was analyzed using Cronbach's alpha, correlation and regression in SPSS software. The results of this study show that employee empowerment has a positive impact on job satisfaction. This study makes it clear that a satisfied worker or employee will be truly productive.

Keywords: Empowerment, Employee Empowerment, Job Satisfaction, Manufacturing Industries.

I. INTRODUCTION

Empowerment: - The term 'empowerment', which became popular since the 1980s, is used to refer to new forms of employee participation. The history of its first definition goes back to 1788. Empowerment is the initial, fundamental and a wonderful component in success and growth for any business enterprise and enhances productivity. Collins (1995) sees that as a limited type of empowerment, at its end, workers are empowered only in the sense that they have greater responsibility to act within a narrow scope and then they are given control over their limited range of action. Hickey and Casner-Lotto (1998:58) say that empowerment means delegating directly to non-management employees a significant amount of decision-making authority that is usually reserved for managers.

Employee Empowerment: - Employees are most important for any organization, hence we can say that employees are the assets of the organization. Empowerment provides employees with the opportunity to grow through complete freedom, greater responsibility, or perhaps a new job altogether. According to a study, eight out of ten employees believe that empowerment is very important for job satisfaction and achieving

organizational goals. When employees are motivated to develop new skill sets and increase productivity, they are more likely to Lawler (1986) argued that employee empowerment involves four distinct processes: knowledge, information, power, and rewards. Quinn and Spreitzer (1999) noted that there is a growing consensus that employee empowerment can be a source of competitive advantage for contemporary organizations. According to Richard Kathnelson, 'Empowerment is the process in which it is realized and to be treated as if the person is in power and to feel as if he is the owner of the firm.

Job satisfaction: - Job satisfaction is most important for any organization. When employees are satisfied with the job and feel that they are in the right place in their job, their performance is better and they are more likely to stay in the company for a long time. When the environment, attitude and quality of work provided to them keeping in mind the overall feelings at the workplace, they will perform better in their work and will contribute significantly in achieving the goals of the organization. Spector, 1997:- Job satisfaction is an assessment of the overall job experience, and arises from several factors such as relationship with the supervisor, sense of work fulfillment, perceived congruence between pay and

work output, and physical conditions of the working environment. According to Edwin Locke, 1969, job satisfaction can be defined as a pleasant emotional state resulting from the appraisal of achieving or facilitating the achievement of one's job values.

Problem Statement:

How does employee empowerment affect job satisfaction levels?

While employee empowerment has a significant relationship with job satisfaction, some differences have also been found that indicate differences in the relationship between the two. The study attempted to connect the larger relational flow between employee empowerment and job satisfaction. Some difficulties were encountered in collecting the sample as not all employees were willing to participate in the study. The relationship between these two elements; However, the sample population included one small facility and the analysis did not differentiate between job-types. Thus, the relationship between employee empowerment and job satisfaction was not fully investigated in a large manufacturing organization with all production processes. Examining both relationships independently in a large manufacturing organization appears relevant and may be applicable to other businesses as well.

literature reviews:

Muhammad Haroon Ameer, Salim Bhatti, Sajid Baig (2014):- The independent variable empowerment was weakly to moderately correlated with the dependent variable job satisfaction. Therefore it is concluded that employee empowerment has a positive impact on job satisfaction.

Dr. Surekha Rana, Vandana Singh (2016), results show that employee empowerment had a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction. The results also confirm significant differences between the empowerment level and job satisfaction level of male and female employees. According to the analysis, male employees are more satisfied with their jobs than female employees. Anu Kohli, Alka

Sharma(2017), The paper also proves that public sector employees are more engaged with their jobs than private sector employees.

Are more satisfied. Studies show that the factors that contribute to job satisfaction are gender specific in nature. Ultimately it can be concluded that employee empowerment can be used as a powerful tool to provide job satisfaction to employees. Abdisa and Fitvi, (2016) observed that both the dimensions of empowerment – behavioral and Psychological have a positive impact on employee job satisfaction. Studies conducted in various industries have revealed a positive relationship between employee empowerment and job satisfaction. Satish Kumar M, S.Abdul Sjalid (2019) it is concluded that empowered employees are more satisfied with their work and this leads to Employee performance increases. Ni Med Anggreyani1, I Gustibagus Honor Satya2 (2020), The results of this study revealed that job satisfaction has a positive impact on organizational commitment, empowerment has a positive impact on organizational commitment, and job stress has a negative impact on organizational commitment. Rana and Singh (2015) investigated the impact of empowerment on job satisfaction in a public sector unit in Haridwar. The findings revealed that empowerment had a significant impact on job satisfaction. Empowerment had a significant impact on job satisfaction of all managers i.e. top level, middle and junior level.

Relationship between Employee Environment and Job Satisfaction.

Many researches have been conducted to establish the relationship between employee empowerment and employee job satisfaction. It has been observed that both dimensions of empowerment – behavioral and psychological, have a positive impact on employee job satisfaction. (Holdsworth and Cartwright, 2003) Employees in call centers are generally more stressed and less satisfied with their jobs. And they have worse physical and mental health than workers in traditional offices. They also have negative perception about empowerment.(Hanyasha and Tahir, 2016) conducted their study on administrative and academic staff in public universities and concluded

that empowerment has a significantly positive impact on job satisfaction. (Kasemap, 2013) indicated that there is a relationship between psychological empowerment, job satisfaction, organizational citizenship behavior and organizational performance; Job satisfaction and psychological empowerment are also positively related.

Table1:represents various factor affecting employee empowerment and job satisfaction.

VARIABLES	RELATIONSHIP	FACTOR
Employee Empowerment	Positive Relation	better quality work, higher productivity, collaboration
	Negative Relation	Turnover, Operational cost, interpersonal relation
Job Satisfaction	Positive Relation	Productivity improvement, better revenue, Promotion
	Negative Relation	Work Stress, emotional exhaustion

Table 1: Factor effecting Employee Empowerment & Job Satisfaction.

II. HYPOTHESIS

Ho: There is no significant relationship between empowerment and job satisfaction.

H1: There is a significant positive relationship between employee empowerment and job satisfaction.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this research study is to establish concrete information regarding the impact of employee empowerment on job satisfaction. The assumptions and theories used to understand the concept of employee empowerment will be reviewed. This research will be able to make a connection between the issue of employee empowerment and job satisfaction. The objective of this study is to investigate how empowerment plays its role towards job satisfaction. To assess the role of

empowerment on employee job satisfaction, there are objectives that need to be considered.

- To discuss and analyze the concept of empowerment in organizations.
- Evaluate and identify the benefits of employee empowerment in organizations.
- To investigate the relationship between employee job satisfaction and employee empowerment.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sampling:

This study was conducted in the manufacturing sector of industrial belt Chandigarh, Panchkula area in Tricity. 100 employees were included in this study but 90 out of 100 employees participated in the questionnaire. The sample size taken was of respondents from this area. The researcher has used judgmental and convenience sampling based technique to collect data from employees of manufacturing industries, questionnaire has been used as a measure to accomplish the research objectives. To collect data, questionnaires were distributed among the employees of the concerned area. The questionnaire consisted of two sections, through the first section information was sought about employee empowerment and through the second section information about job satisfaction was sought. The questionnaire was measured on a 5 point Likert scale, where 5 means strongly agree and 1 means strongly disagree.

Analysis Tool: Descriptive method was used. SPSS was used for analysis. Data was analyzed using Cronbach's alpha, correlation and regression in SPSS software.

Questionnaire Design:

It contained 20 questions, all of which were single-choice questions and easy to understand. The design of the questionnaire was based on literature review. The questions were designed by us and included key elements related to employee empowerment and job satisfaction. The purpose of the questionnaire was to investigate whether there is a significant relationship between employee empowerment and job satisfaction, each question was not more than

two lines. Five scale points of agreement can be selected by the participants, which are strongly agree (5 points for this), agree (4 points), neutral (3 points), disagree (2 points) and strongly disagree. (1 point). These scales proved to be very helpful in making a convenient measure of consumer attitudes.

The Target Population: The targeted sample for this study comprises of Top, Middle and lower level of employees.

V. DATA ANALYSIS

Correlation

Pearson Correlation	1	.352**
Sig.(2-tailed)	90	.001
N		90
Job Satisfaction	.352**	1
Sig.(2-Tailed)	.001	
N	90	90

2. Model Summary (a&b)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of The Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	Df1	Df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.351 ^a	.123	.113	3.17038	.123	12.349	1	89	.001	1.769

a. Predictor: (constant), Empowerment

b. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

3. ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	124.109	1	124.109	12.348	.001 ^a
Regression	884.513	89	10.051		
Residual Total	1008.622	90			

a. Predictors: (constant), empowerment

b. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Reliability:

Case Processing Summary

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Interpretation: The correlation between empowerment and job satisfaction is .351 which is a positive correlation.

Regression

1. Correlations

	Empowerment	Job Satisfaction
Pearson Correlation	.351	1.000
Empowerment	1.000	.351
Job Satisfaction		
Sig.(1-tailed)		
Empowerment	.000	
Job Satisfaction		.000
N Empowerment	90	90
Job Satisfaction	90	90

Case	Valid	N	%
	90	90	100.0
	Excluded	0	.0
	Total	90	100.0

a. List wise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Test:

Cronbach's Alpha	No. Of Item
.519	20

Interpretation: The value of Cronbach,s Alpha is .519 that is below the required level that is .7. The reason behind is that the questionnaire is made by student but not taken from previous researches.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study understands the impact of employee empowerment on employee job satisfaction.

Literature shows a positive relationship between employee empowerment and job satisfaction. Empowerment is based on the idea that by providing employees with skills, resources, rights, opportunities, motivation- Also holding them responsible and accountable for the results of their work will contribute to their potential and satisfaction. Job satisfaction can be measured through various dimensions such as promotion, salary, supervision, working conditions, co-workers and the work itself.

The level of job satisfaction of employees in different sectors varies from each other. People in the public sector are more satisfied with their jobs as compared to the employees in the private sector. Therefore, it can be concluded that the employees have job satisfaction. To provide that, employee empowerment can be used as a powerful tool, the results of this study show that employee empowerment has a positive impact on job satisfaction. This study makes it clear that a satisfied worker or employee will be truly productive.

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